

Innovation process support tools for the first round of CoDIEs

Deliverable 3.3

M18/SEPT 2024

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**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101084179.

Project Full Title	ClimateSmartAdvisors: Connecting and mobilizing the EU agricultural advisory community to support the transition to Climate Smart Farming
GA number	101084179
Type of Action	Coordination and Support Action (CSA)
Project Duration	84 months
Project Start Date	01.04.2023
Project Website	climatesmartadvisors.eu
Deliverable Title	Innovation process support tools for first round of CoDIEs
Deliverable Submission Date	30.09.2024
Version	V1.0
Dissemination Level	PU – Public
Deliverable Lead	EV ILVO
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Work Package	WP3
Keywords	[co-design, innovation, dynamic capabilities, transition, multi-level perspective]

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Please note that the review of this document is still in progress, and the deliverable is subject to final approval. Any feedback or changes provided during this review process may affect the final version, and approval from the relevant parties is required before the deliverable is considered complete.

Glossary

Advisory Services (AS): The activities that are performed by advisors to create knowledge and Know-how in individual and/or collective learning processes.

Advisory Service Provider (ASP): Organizational bodies engaged with advisory service.

Climate Smart Advisor (CSA): Advisor who takes part in a 2-year CoP with their peers, meeting on min. 4 times per year and supported by the project with a number of CoP activities, including both training and peer learning activities.

Climate Smart Farming (CSF): An approach that helps guide actions to transform agri-food systems towards green and climate resilient practices.

Co-Design Innovation Experiment (CoDIEs): MA practice-oriented innovation experiments where CSAs play a central role as change and innovation agents in CSF multi-level transitions. CoDIEs (8-10) fill in innovation gaps that have been identified in CSA activities in CSF MIPs across the EU (**Complementary definition in section 3**).

Climate Smart Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (CS AKIS): System of actors, stakeholders and organisations at regional, national or EU level who interact in support of mutual learning, to generate, share, and use CS related knowledge and information.

Multi-actor (MA): The co-creation and sharing of knowledge among different types of actors with complementary expertise (**Complementary definition in section 3.2.1**).

Multi-actor innovation project (MIP): A project bringing together different types of actors (e.g., farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers) with complementary types of knowledge and skills with the aim to innovate together EU.

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Revision history

Version	Date	Reviewer	Modifications
[Draft 0.1]		Jorieke Potters (WR)	Feedback on structure and main focus of the document; minor textual and layout corrections
[Draft 0.2]	15/10/2024	EV ILVO, UAL	Restructuring of the document, revision of section 4
[Final 1.0]	28/10/2024	Lies Debruyne	final corrections, version for upload

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1 Abstract

Deliverable 3.3 outlines the setup and support process for selected Co-Design Innovation Experiments (CoDIEs), emphasizing a multi-actor, multi-level approach to achieve climate smart farming goals. The document serves as a resource for CoDIEs partners, supporting internal project action, but can provide inspiration to anyone working multi-actor innovation projects and/or processes.

CoDIEs are collaborative experiments that engage multiple actors to co-create and implement climate-smart farming (CSF) innovations. These initiatives aim to address agricultural challenges by fostering cooperation between diverse stakeholders, including farmers, advisors, researchers, and policymakers. Advisors and Advisory Service Providers (ASPs) have the potential to be pivotal in guiding these processes, promoting the adoption of innovative practices, and facilitating communication across various levels of the agricultural knowledge and innovation system (AKIS). CoDIEs seek to explore local needs through co-designed innovations that contribute to sustainable agricultural practices while considering multi-level transitions within the farming ecosystem. The selection of CoDIEs involved an application process, resulting in 3 selected projects for the 1st round of CoDIEs.

To facilitate the transition to climate-smart farming, CoDIEs need to develop dynamic capabilities that allows to engage with various stakeholders at multiple levels, including individual farmers and policymakers. CoDIEs operate within a systems concept, requiring both tangible and intangible resources, which are essential for implementing solutions and innovations in agriculture. The CoDIE process involves several key steps that emphasize action research, where participants engage in iterative reflection and practical activities tailored to their specific contexts. A series of workshops and coaching sessions will guide CoDIE coordinators in creating action plans and selecting appropriate innovation support tools to enhance their effectiveness. Ongoing follow-up meetings and a closing workshop will provide opportunities for reflection, peer learning, and evaluation of progress in achieving the CoDIEs' objectives.

2 Introduction

In ClimateSmartAdvisors, advisors are recognised as being in a key position in developing and sharing climate smart (CS) innovations and good practices between peers and with farmers. Therefore, ClimateSmartAdvisors works on improving the opportunities, knowledge, dynamic capabilities, and skills of agricultural advisors to support farmers in the implementation of climate change mitigation and adaption actions across Europe. The project aims to boost the role of agricultural advisors and advisory service providers (ASP) across multiple levels by strengthening their capacity in providing targeted advice on climate mitigation and adaptation approaches, and by sharing solutions for impactful advisory methods. By boosting the role of the EU agricultural advisory community, we aim to contribute to an acceleration of the adoption of climate smart farming (CSF) practices by the wider farming community within and across EU Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKISs).

ClimateSmartAdvisors work package (WP3) “Strengthening the role of advisors in CSF MIPs”, in particular, has as its main objective to explore, understand and support the role of Climate Smart Advisors (CSAs) in CSF innovation processes and the multi-level transition to CSF practices, both by compiling and analysing ongoing CSA multi-actor innovation projects (MIPs) and by locating CSAs at the centre of co-design innovation experiments (CoDIEs). The CoDIEs have been selected from project partners' proposals, based on a white spot analysis and a criteria matrix, as elaborated in Deliverable 3.1. The selected CoDIEs will serve as case studies to analyse the role of CSAs as central actors in innovation processes to support the multi-level transition to CSF, and to provide tools and materials to better engage a wide range of advisors in CSF innovation activities.

Deliverable 3.3 is situated in Task 3.3, which focuses specifically on the set-up and support of CoDIEs. The set-up and selection of the first round of CoDIEs is covered in more detail by Milestone document 24, and is only briefly addressed in this Deliverable, which focuses on the support offered to the CoDIEs. While the original objective of this deliverable was to present an overview of innovation process support tools that could be used by the CoDIEs to establish their activities, the scope has been extended, to encompass the overall process and approach for supporting and coaching the CoDIEs during their activities. The initial setting up of the CoDIEs through the roadmap exercise allows the CoDIEs to identify in what areas innovation tools are necessary to reach their goals in terms of CSF, through a multi-actor, multi-level approach. To this end, we make specific reference to existing resources for innovation process tools and methods which might be helpful in this process. This document is in the first place targeted at CoDIEs partners, aiming to support internal project actions. However, this document can provide inspiration on methodologies and approaches for anyone who is involved or supporting multi-actor innovation projects and/or processes.

The deliverable is structured as follows: following this introduction section, we provide some background on what CoDIEs are in the context of CSA, and introduce the three selected CoDIEs for the first round in Section 3. In Section 4, we then focus on the process for guiding and supporting the CoDIEs during their implementation. It starts with a brief introduction on the concept of dynamic capabilities, as a basis for both the analysis and development of the CoDIEs. After that we describe, in 6 distinct steps, what actions will be taken to support the CoDIEs.

3 CoDIEs: Co-Design Innovation Experiments

CoDIEs are multi-actor, multi-level experiments focused on co-creation and implementation of CSF innovations. CoDIEs involve various actors working together on a specific topic to enable a considerable move towards CSF in practice, which includes having influence on various levels, as illustrated in Figure 1 below, and further elaborated under 3.1.3. In these experiments, advisors and ASPs are expected to play a central role as agents that promote the exchange of knowledge and ideas among AKIS actors, encourage the adoption of climate-smart practices resulting from the co-creation processes and participate in the dissemination of the results to consolidate these practices across the various levels of agricultural activities

Figure 1: Multi-level, multi-actor approach in CSA (source: CSA Grant Agreement)

Through the CoDIEs, it is intended to:

- Establish multi-actor, multi-level experiments at the farm system level to explore innovation processes on CSF aimed at filling the white spots in MIPs and advisory gaps in CSF innovations that were identified (see Deliverable 3.1).
- Promote the development and exchange of innovations and CS good practices among advisors, farmers and other actors in the AKIS network.
- Strengthen the role of farm advisors and ASPs to improve their capacity to provide advice in the processes of innovation and implementation of CSF practices.
- Explore how the participation/engagement of farm advisors and ASPs can be improved at different levels/stages of the transition to CSF.

3.1 Characteristics of CoDIEs

3.1.1 Multi-actor in the context of the CoDIEs

Working in a “multi-actor” way is a bottom-up/transversal cooperation/co-creation between actors with necessary and complementary expertise, skills and knowledge, and with different interests and perspectives. This implies that the CoDIEs team must consist of different partners engaging in a multidirectional exchange, where the necessary practical, scientific and other complementary knowledge and/or skills of the different actors are combined to solve a specific problem.: . Depending on the goal of the project, these actors or partners can include:

- farmers / farmers' groups and associations, foresters /foresters' groups and associations, aquaculture producers, fishers / fishers' groups and associations;
- researchers;
- advisors;
- food and bio economy businesses, other businesses;
- consumer associations, local communities, citizens, civil society organisations including NGOs; and
- government representatives.

For the CoDIEs it is expected that at least three types of actors in addition to the advisors (e.g., farmers, researchers, input/technology suppliers, policy makers, citizens...) are involved. Each CoDIE also has an assigned “CoDIE coordinator”. The CoDIE coordinator is working for a ClimateSmartAdvisors project partner or affiliated entity, and is preferably active as an advisor, since it is expected that advisors and/or Advisory Service Providers (ASPs) play a central and indispensable role in the CoDIE with regard to planning, development and/or exchange of innovations, knowledge and expertise. The person who acts as the CoDIE coordinator is expected to have a good understanding of both innovation process dynamics and technical content, and to have at least basic facilitation skills, to ensure a positive and constructive multi-actor group dynamic.

3.1.2 Co-designed and practice-oriented innovation

CoDIEs should co-develop (with other actors of the AKIS network) innovations, be it economic, social, organisational/business model, product, design, service/market innovations, that address practical local problems, needs and/or opportunities in the agricultural sector and contribute to its transition towards CSF.

3.1.3 CSF multi-level transitions

Climate-Smart Farming (CSF) is an approach that helps guide actions to transform agri-food systems towards sustainable and climate-resilient practices. The main objectives of CSF are to adapt and increase resilience to climate change; mitigate or reduce greenhouse gas emissions; and maintain or sustainably increase agricultural productivity and incomes;. To contribute to accelerating the transition to CSF, advisors/ASP need to have the capacity to work in a multi-level perspective, i.e. considering the different stages of the transition process (preparation, experimentation, coalescing around ideas, consolidation and resilience building). Also, advisors/ASP, should not only have a joint working approach with individuals or groups of farmers and their farm businesses, but also with other actors and organisations aiming at influencing business environments or AKIS, policy makers, etc.

In multi-level transitions, innovative CSF activities, carried out at the experimental niche level within their agricultural context and AKIS, have the potential to influence and change the dominant narrative at the second level, i.e. the level of the agricultural system, which includes technologies, institutions and actors. These innovation experiments are also expected to influence changes at the third level (meta-narrative), i.e. the consolidation and recognition of CSF practices as an integral part of farming systems (figure 1).

In the context of CSA, the selected CoDIEs can start from either one, or more, of the three aforementioned levels. It is not expected that the CoDIEs will be implemented at all levels of the transition to CSF, but it is expected that they will be designed considering how from any given level, it is planned to influence the other levels of the transition, e.g. through meetings, working groups, peer-to-peer learning with other AKIS actors, lobbying, policy initiatives or similar.

3.1.4 Advisors as central actors in CoDIEs

Farm advisors are considered key actors to share new knowledge and ideas as an integral part of a stronger AKIS and to contribute to the development of innovation projects and the dissemination of their results. To influence the transition towards CSF systems, advisors and/or ASPs in the CoDIEs will play an indispensable role in the planning, developing and exchange of innovations and climate-smart good practices among peers, with farmers and other key stakeholders in the AKIS network.

3.2 Selected CoDIEs

A full description of the application and selection process for the CoDIEs is available in the CSA Milestone 24 document (included as Annex 1). In short, a guideline was developed and shared with potential applicants (= project beneficiaries) on June 17th 2024, followed by a webinar on June 18th. The guideline document served as a reference document for applicants to understand how the proposal should be developed. In parallel with the guidelines, an application form was also shared with the potential applicants. After that date, the WP3 team remained available for questions from interested partners, and support them in the application process. The application remained opened from July 1st – Sept 22nd 2024, after which we received 8 submitted proposals. All proposals were evaluated and scored by an Evaluation and Selection Committee, leading to the selection of 3 CoDIEs for this first round. A 4th CoDIE, submitted by a UK partner, has been selected pending funding availability (Table 1). The CoDIEs selected in this first round will have an implementation time between 18 and 24 months. The aim is that the insights/lessons learned in this first round will be analysed and integrated in the second round of CoDIEs (min. 5) planned for March 2027 (MS25). Therefore, start and end dates can be flexible but should start between 1st November 2024 (M20) and end no later than 1st November 2026 (M44).

Table 1: Overview of the selected CoDIEs. UK partners are associated partners in ClimateSmartAdvisors, and are thus not eligible for direct funding. The CoDIE nr. 4 will be included in the process pending funding availability.

Nr	Title	Country (specific region, if applicable)	Coordinating organisation	Main objective
1	Rural energy community St-Ruprecht	Austria (Styria)	LK Steiermark	to develop a sustainable energy community that integrates electricity production with an existing biomass-based district heating network operated by farmers, supported by the guidance of advisors.
2	Empowering farmers to strengthen advisory services: building a demo farm network and digital tools for regenerative agriculture in Slovakia	Slovak Republic	Bioeconomy Cluster	to strengthen advisory services within the AKIS in Slovakia through i) the initiation of a support scheme for a demonstration farm network and ii) the development and testing of the digital tool "Rege-PODCAST" for exchange and dissemination of knowledge among farmers and advisors focused on regenerative agriculture.
3	Biodiversity friendly farming	Serbia	Biosense	to develop and promote sustainable agricultural protocols that align pest management with environmental sustainability. A key objective is to adapt existing fruit orchards to regenerative agriculture principles, biocontrol strategies, and sustainable beekeeping practices.
4	Climate Smart Circular Nutrient Network	United Kingdom	Innovation for Agriculture	<i>To explore the use of organic fertilisers, derived through anaerobic digestion from intensive poultry farming, in arable farming, particularly in phosphorus-deficient areas like the Cotswolds. Field trials, designed and managed by farmers and advisors, will assess the impact of those fertilisers on crop productivity, soil health, water quality, and carbon emissions.</i>

4 Guidance and support for the CoDIEs

4.1 Understanding and developing dynamic capabilities as basis for the CoDIE activities

To accelerate the transition to climate smart farming, advisors and ASPs must be able to work on multiple levels, that is, with individual farmers, groups of farmers, and their farm businesses, but also with other actors and organizations with the goal of influencing business or AKIS environments, policymakers, etc. Advisors and ASPs can also be part of changing the narrative of what climate-smart farming and advising mean. To meet the real-life challenges faced in agriculture, the co-creation of solutions between farmers, scientists, enterprises, and advisors crosses the boundaries of technical, organizational, economic, and social innovation. Thus, in addition to their important role in updating knowledge, skills, and competences in their interactions with farmers, ASPs have a crucial role to play in CS innovations within their context and agri-systems. We consider that CoDIEs exist within this “systems” concept.

In the context of agricultural sustainability and making the transition to CSF a reality, CoDIEs need both resources and capabilities to act or influence such transitions and to reach their goals. It is important to understand the interconnectedness between resources and capabilities. Resources can be defined as tangible and intangible assets that can either be owned or accessed by CoDIE participants and stakeholders. Resources are used to create value, achieve specific objectives, and solve problems through material, financial, human, or organizational resources. For instance, tangible resources may be machinery, funds, experimental buildings, etc. while intangible resources may be knowledge, human resources or collaborations for knowledge exchange and further innovation.

On the other hand, capabilities are defined by the technological and organizational/individual abilities that allow the CoDIE to make use of these resources. Capabilities are required to mobilize resources, while the resources are needed to develop capabilities. However, the concept of capability is not static and refers to more than simple “know-how”, especially in dynamic contexts such as a CoDIE where the participants are responding to external factors, influences and environments.

This is where “dynamic capabilities” are particularly needed. Dynamic capabilities have the ability to reorganize and acquire assets (resources and skills) that the CoDIE will have or would like to have, not only to respond to changing environments but also to increase its capacity for innovation, resilience, and adaptation. According to Helfat, dynamic capabilities involve adaptation and change, as they build, integrate, and reconfigure other resources and capabilities (Helfat et al., 2007). Dynamic capabilities are built across multi-levels and different phases of the transitional process to CSF. The central idea of the dynamic capabilities approach is the relation between an entity’s resources and the capabilities to further build and create new resources or modify and improve existing resources (Helfat et al., 2007).

4.2 CoDIEs process steps and timeline

With 3 CoDIEs selected, and at least 5 more to start in the second round, we expect that there will be considerable diversity within the selected experiments. This diversity is expected to be manifested in terms of production sectors, thematic areas and climate challenges on which they intend to focus. For the first round of CoDIEs, we have one CoDIE focusing on creating a rural energy community in Austria, a second one focused on biodiversity friendly farming in Serbia, and a third one which aims to strengthen advisory services with a focus on regenerative agriculture in Slovakia. Furthermore, in the CoDIEs pool we expect to have different levels of maturity, where some initiatives are just starting, and others are more mature collaborations, which will have an effect on the type of activities they will be performing. Also, considering the composition of our consortium, we expect that different types of advisory organisations, positioned differently within national AKISs, will take the lead. The difference in position within the national CS-AKIS, and the overall composition of the CS-AKIS will again be important elements to consider in organising and implementing the process of innovation and transformation. These and many other differences will influence the functioning and development of the CoDIEs, meaning that each CoDIE will follow their own path and pace. However, all CoDIEs function within a common framework, as described in the previous section (4.1), and will follow similar steps, even if on a different path.

The steps follow the general spirit of an action research approach. Action research can be understood as research which seeks to „bring together action and reflection, theory and practice, in participation with others, in the pursuit of practical solutions to issues of pressing concern to people“ (Reason & Bradbury, 2006). It suggests a combination of taking action and doing research, linked together by critical reflection. As part of this action research approach, we will guide each of the CoDIEs through a number of common steps (Figure 2). During these steps, we focus on well-considered actions, considering the contexts in which the CoDIEs are operating and each of their specified objectives, and joint reflection, with the ultimate goal of creating change in their national context. Each of these steps are further elaborated below.

Figure 2: Overview of the main research steps and activities for the CoDIEs

It is important to note that the research steps, as visualised in Figure 2, will take place in parallel with CoDIE-specific activities, i.e. activities which the CoDIEs will conduct to reach their CoDIE objective. These will be different for each CoDIE, are based on what has been described in the CoDIE applications, and are designed and led by the CoDIE coordinators. The CoDIE-specific activities are not included in Figure 2, and will also not be discussed in detail in this document. As part of the CoDIEs proposal, a first overview has been drafted of those CoDIE-specific activities. However, the research process is designed to support an iterative process of action, reflection and refinement of those CoDIE-specific activities.

4.2.1 CoDIEs online kick-off meeting (January 2025)

The objectives of the CoDIEs kick-off workshop are i) to introduce the WP3 team, the selected CoDIEs, and the CoDIEs coordinators, ii) to familiarise CoDIE coordinators with the concept of dynamic capabilities as conceptual basis for the development of CoDIEs and iii) to introduce the different planned CoDIEs research steps and activities. The meeting will be held online, and is expected to take approximately 2 hours.

During the kick-off meeting, specific attention will be given on the procedures for developing the roadmap for an action plan, based on 5 distinct steps (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Visual representation of the CoDIEs roadmap

This roadmap provides guidance for the implementation of CoDIEs and includes an analysis of the conditions necessary to establish them. The framework will assist CoDIE teams in defining the problems and boundaries of their CoDIEs. The first step involves mapping the aims, boundaries, and purposes while considering all key stakeholder perspectives. The second step focuses on defining the CoDIE problem in a consensual and accurate manner with stakeholder involvement. The third step is identifying and analyzing current participants and potential future stakeholders. The fourth step, which is divided into two parts, focuses on identifying the CoDIEs resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations. This is followed by an assessment of the conditions for co-creation, innovation, and transitions, allowing for ongoing evaluation and comparative analysis of progress over time. Finally, a strategy and action plan will be developed, consolidating all information and insights from the previous stages to ensure a clear roadmap for achieving the CoDIEs goals. For each of these steps, the necessary resources/materials/tools will be provided to facilitate their implementation.

- Step 1 – Defining CoDIE boundaries: The aim of this step is to understand and delimit the CoDIEs according to their objectives, purposes, activities and the context in which they are located. This step allows for defining initial parameters and possible impacts and results, serving as a prerequisite for subsequent steps.
- Step 2 – CoDIE Problem Definition: The main goal of this step is to outline the challenges faced by farmers and stakeholders in dealing with climate issues. It offers a framework to pinpoint the core climate problems addressed by CoDIEs, shaping their purpose, facilitating the integration of necessary innovations for accelerated solution development.
- Step 3 – Stakeholder identification and analysis: This step is helpful to grasp the landscape of the CoDIEs situation, it is essential to comprehend the identity and involvement of stakeholders, recognizing their roles and influence in collaboratively shaping solutions. It is important to identify and maintain a balance among stakeholders emphasizing a multi-actor approach
- Step 4A – Identifying resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations (RCCIs) This step aims to enhance the knowledge and skills of stakeholders by identifying future RCCIs. These are crucial for setting objectives based on available and missing RCCIs. They also play a vital role in designing climate-smart solutions, solving problems, and scaling initiatives. Analysing RCCIs helps to understand how actors respond to dynamic environments in the transition to sustainable agriculture. It also guides the formulation of an action plan by correlating objectives with identified problems and addressing the gap between current and desired states based on RCCIs.
- Step 4B – Assessing conditions for co-creation, innovation, and transition: This tool assesses CoDIEs conditions for co-creation, innovation, and transitioning to climate-smart farming, generating a spider diagram from a survey. CoDIEs can easily evaluate their resources, capabilities, collaborations, and innovations, contributing to the strategy and action planning.
- Step 5 – Strategy and action plan: The action plan is important for defining concrete activities to achieve climate objectives, using existing RCCIs or addressing gaps, for instance through the selection and incorporation of specific innovation process support tools (see 4.2.3) as needed. It forms the basis for ongoing planning, provides data for monitoring and evaluation, and allows for periodic adjustments based on progress and lessons learned.

To develop the action plan, CoDIE coordinators will be expected to conduct a series of workshop exercises (during one full day, or various half days) with their CoDIEs team. For each of these workshop exercises, templates are provided by the WP3 team, to assist the CoDIEs coordinators, which will be presented during the kick-off meeting. During the meeting, we will also consider how the CoDIEs proposal was set up, and discuss if and how the CoDIEs coordinators can benefit from work conducted during the proposal stage, to develop their action plan.

4.2.2 Local in-person CoDIEs workshops for action plan development (Jan – March 2025)

Following the CoDIEs kick-off meeting, CoDIE coordinators will have 2 months to conduct the workshops, as elaborated during the kick-off workshop, with their CoDIEs team. Based on these workshops, CoDIE coordinators are expected to prepare a completed action plan for their CoDIE (Step 5 in the Roadmap). Considering the preparatory work that was done during the application phase, this will not start from scratch, but it is expected that this can build on the proposal that was submitted during the CoDIEs application.

The CoDIEs action plan will need to be sent to the WP3 team, who will do a review of the action plans.

4.2.3 Online individual coaching meetings for selection of innovation support tools (March 2025 – end of the CoDIE)

Following the delivery of the action plans, one-on-one meetings will be scheduled with the ILVO team and CoDIEs coordinators to go through the different steps and the planned activities. The review and one-on-one meetings will focus on the possible inclusion of innovation tools and facilitation methods that can support the CoDIEs in their development. The goal will be to see if the planned activities are 'fit-for-purpose & context'. The selection of innovation process support tools will be guided by the outputs of the roadmap exercise, particularly the analysis of "gaps" where innovation tools may be needed. The innovation support team (ILVO) is available to coach CoDIE coordinators in this process of identifying innovation support tools, and help them further (re)(de)fine and (re)design national activities.

The decision to work with individualised coaching to further support the CoDIE coordinators in implementing the different activities in the action plan in their local contexts, is there to offer maximum flexibility, accommodating the diversity within the relatively small number of selected CoDIEs. Depending on the outcomes of the roadmap exercise, but also on e.g. CoDIE coordinators competency levels for managing innovation and multi-actor processes, we will offer guidance on what could be useful tools and methods to use in their specific context. Coaching will be organised by the ILVO team during specific moments (online coaching meetings after completion of the action plan, and during or shortly after the follow-up meetings), but coaching meetings can be requested at any time to support CoDIE coordinators in the design and management of their CoDIE activities. If participants believe it is valuable, a WhatsApp group will be created for the WP3 support team and the CoDIE managers of the selected CoDIEs to enable easy exchanges about the CoDIEs experiences.

To support the coaching process, we will rely on a wealth of existing resources, where a wide range of tools and methods, both for innovation support and for facilitating multi-actor interaction and cooperation, have been described. Key starting point will be the work done by three other currently active Horizon projects. First, as part of the PREMIERE project (<https://premiere-multiactor.eu/>) an extensive [repository](#) is being created of specific tools/toolkits/guidelines that can be used in multi-actor settings. The repository is currently in the form of an Excel database, but will in a later stage be transformed into an online repository. PREMIERE's ambition is to gather various tools and databases of tools in support of more streamlined, cohesive and efficient multi-actor proposal processes. While their focus is specifically on the proposal stage of MA projects, the databases and individual tools which have been gathered are not exclusively focused on this, but have a much wider scope, gathering databases and tools developed for very diverse purposes, e.g. toolkits for responsible research and innovation, tools to support and sustain thriving networks, facilitation and stakeholder engagement tools, etc. The repository currently holds 48 tool databases, providing a short description, information on the provider and the type of tools in the toolkit, and a link to the resource. Also, 43 tools are described in more detail, indicating the type of tool (e.g. workshop format, process outline, template, online whiteboard, reflection exercise, online collaboration software, ...), the target group (leader, follower, self-initiator, invitee), the timing of use (in connection to the proposal process; multi-actor approach basics, consortium-building, proposal-writing, work programme design, supporting reflection), the type of activity it supports, the source and link(s) to further information.

Second and third, there are the Attractiss (<https://attractiss.eu/>) and ModernAKIS (<https://modernakis.eu/>) projects, which both have a shared focus on supporting agricultural innovation. The former addresses the role of innovation support services in these processes, while the latter is centered around the creation of more efficient and effective Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS). Both projects have joined forces to develop the AKISConnect platform (<https://www.akisconnect.eu/>), which hosts different resources, including a toolkit for innovation

support. The toolkit provides tools and methods specifically tailored for innovation support service providers in agriculture, and currently holds 46 tools. Tools can be searched based on the innovation phase for which they are appropriate (initial idea, inspiration, planning, development, realization, dissemination, embedding), format (support for farmer groups vs. support for farmers one-on-one), and needed preparation and execution time. For each of the tools a short description is available, and links to additional materials and resources are included.

The use of these existing resources will be done in cooperation with these other projects, meaning that we will also offer feedback to those projects about the use of the tools in their repositories in the context of the CoDIEs. We also remain conscious of the fact that the objectives and frames of the other projects are not fully aligned to the CoDIEs framework, which is built on the multi-level perspective and the concept of dynamic capabilities. We will thus always keep an open view and evaluate if the existing tools and resources are fit for supporting multi-level transitions and developing dynamic capabilities, and if and where the existing repositories may have gaps. In case we identify potential gaps, we will extend our search for suitable tools and methods.

4.2.4 Follow-up meeting 1 (May-June 2025) & follow-up meeting 2 (January/February 2026)

The objectives of the follow-up meetings are i) to review the progress for each of the individual CoDIEs action plans, and ii) to exchange experiences between the CoDIEs coordinators. To support this, the plan is to work with a dedicated monitoring, evaluation and learning template, which will help the CoDIEs coordinators reflect on the actions that were taken, and what this has produced in terms of outputs and outcomes. According to the need to evaluate the process with regard to the multi-level approach, multi-actor transition, dynamic capabilities and the role of advisors in this process, other templates and/or materials may be provided or used during these meetings. The CoDIEs coordinators will have the time to exchange about successes and setbacks in their CoDIE, and will go over the planned activities for the upcoming months. The aim is to discuss possible updates to the action plan, focusing specifically on the use of tools for supporting the innovation process, and moving through different levels in the transition process to CSF. We plan to evaluate, as a group, at which of the multi-levels the CoDIE are operating, and what is needed to further the transition in their local context. Doing this as part of the follow-up meetings also supports peer learning between the CoDIE coordinators on this topic.

Meetings will be organised online, timing and duration is still to be decided.

4.2.5 CoDIEs closing workshop (October 2026)

The main objective of the closing workshop is to understand the process of multi-level, multi-actor transitions process, the role of advisors within it, and the usefulness of innovation tools employed. The exact format and content will be discussed and decided at a later point.

4.2.6 Interviews with CoDIE coordinators & participants

To conclude the process of the 1st group of CoDIEs, CoDIE coordinators are expected to take part in one semi-structured interview. Other participants will also be invited, although in some cases a language barrier will need to be considered. The focus of the interviews, and the interview outline will be decided at a later point.

5 Annex – Milestone 24